

Formylcamphor Condensed with Diamines : The Structure in Solution as Obtained from UV Absorption and Circular Dichroism Spectroscopy

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The condensation products of the stereoisomers of 1,2-diamino-1,2-diphenylethane with two molecules of formylcamphor have been investigated by means of uv absorption and circular dichroism spectroscopy. In chloroform such compounds take on a *syn* configuration with hydrogen bonding within an α -(N-alkylaminoethylene) camphor group, and the intense $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions of the chromophore will couple in dimers provided the chromophores are near to each other. It is demonstrated how information about the relative orientation of the two formylcamphor groups may be obtained using the signs and envelopes of the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition bands.

SCHIFF base condensation products of formylcamphor and various 1,2-diamines have been rather thoroughly investigated and quite different conclusions have been reached concerning the stereochemistry of these compounds in various solvents¹⁻³.

With the purpose of studying further the rotational conformations around substituted ethylene bridges showing that the stereochemistry of these rather complicated compounds can be understood within an exciton formalism, the condensation products between formylcamphor and the stereoisomers of 1,2-diamino-1,2-diphenylethane (stilbenediamine) have been investigated.

It has been the conclusion of previous papers in this subject^{1,2} that minimum potential energy even for closely related molecules can be achieved in quite different ways e.g. in R-chxn(fmCH)₂ and S-chxn(fmCH)₂ the rigidity of the cyclohexane ring is a dominating factor which forces the two diastereoisomers to take Δ and Λ configurations, respectively. The configuration⁴ is given in terms of handedness of the pair of lines connecting N and O of each aminomethylenecamphor group, and thus simultaneously representing the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition dipole moment of the chromophores.

In contrast to this it was shown that when the barrier towards rotation around the C-C bond of the diamine is low, the stereochemistry of the compounds is determined by the asymmetric bulkiness of the camphor skeleton as e.g. R-pn(fmCH)₂ and S-pn(fmCH)₂ have the same absolute configuration of the above mentioned pair of lines (Δ)^{1,2}.

Finally, it was demonstrated that *meso* compounds, e.g. R,S-chxn(fmCH)₂ and R,S-2,3-bn(fmCH)₂, exhibit co-existence of the two possible forms (*e,a*) and (*a,e*) and that equivalence exists in the behaviour between *meso* compounds and compounds with an optically inactive ethylene bridge, e.g. en(fmCH)₂ and ibn(fmCH)₂⁵; spectra of the latter compound have not been published earlier,

but are quite analogous to those of en(fmCH)₂. Therefore at room temperature and in aged chloroform solutions two *gauche* rotamers of the ethylene bridge exist in equilibrium with the *trans* form. The equilibrium, however, may be displaced at lower temperatures, and judged from the CD spectrum of ibn(fmCH)₂ in CHCl₃ at -60° (compare Table 2 of Ref. 1) this should be towards the opposite absolute configuration of R-chxn(fmCH)₂. A consequence of the difference in configuration between R-pn(fmCH)₂ and S-pn(fmCH)₂, on one hand and the *meso* and optically inactive compounds on the other is that, although it looks that the camphor groups are the stereochemically determining factors as soon as the rotation around the ethylene bridge is reasonably free, asymmetric methyl groups on the ethylene bridge are also involved in defining the minimum potential energy. Certainly, it is demonstrated from the above argumentation that formylcamphor Schiff base condensates with 1,2-diamines are compounds where the different substituents are heavily embedded into each other.

Experimental

Racemic stilbenediamine was prepared and resolved according to Williams and Bailar⁶ and Ugo *et al.*⁷, respectively, *meso*-stilbenediamine was prepared according to Irving and Parkins⁸, and formylcamphor was prepared from natural (+)*D*-camphor according to Bishop *et al.*⁹. The identity of the compounds was established through chemical analyses.

Assignments of absolute configuration of optical active diamines have been done according to Gillard⁶.

Ultraviolet absorption spectra were measured with a Cary 14 spectrophotometer and circular dichroism spectra with a Roussel-Jouan dichrograph II.

Fig 1. Molar absorptions and circular dichroisms of various condensates dissolved and aged in CHCl_3 . Full lines : room temperatures, Broken lines : -60° . In cases with broken lines in the CD-spectra no changes occur with temperature. All dipole strengths are $\sim 2.10^{-19} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Abbreviations :

R-stien = (+)_D-(R,R)-1,2-diamino-1,2-diphenyl-ethane
 S-stien = (-)_D-(S,S)-1,2-diamino-1,2-diphenyl-ethane
 R,S-stien = meso-(R,S)-1,2-diamino-1,2-diphenyl-ethane

R-chxn = (-)_D-trans-(R,R)-1,2-cyclohexane-diamine
 S-chxn = (+)_D-trans-(S,S)-1,2-cyclohexane-diamine
 R,S-chxn = meso-(R,S)-1,2-cyclohexanediamine
 R-2,3-bn = (-)_D-(R,R)-2,3-butanediamine
 S-2,3-bn = (+)_D-(S,S)-2,3-butanediamine

R,S-2,3-bn = *meso*-(R,S)-2,3-butanediamine
 R-pn = (-)_D-(R)-1,2-propanediamine
 S-pn = (+)_D-(S)-1,2-propanediamine
 en = 1,2-ethanediamine
 ibn = 2-methyl-1,2-propanediamine
 fmcH = formylcamphor
 R-pn(fmcH)₂ etc. symbolize the "Schiff base"
 condensates formed from one molecule of diamine
 and two molecules of diketones

Results and Discussion

The Schiff base condensates of stilbenediamine and formylcamphor show the same kind of *syn/anti* tautomerisation depending on the ability of the solvent to form hydrogen bonds, as was demonstrated earlier for similar compounds¹, and accordingly we will, in what follows, only refer to the spectra of aged chloroform solutions. In such solution it is possible by ¹H nmr spectroscopy to confirm that the *syn* configuration of the chromophore is the dominating species. The reason why we wish to be certain that we work with the *syn* configuration is that we want to discuss spectral behaviour in an exciton formalism with reference to the acetylacetone chromophore⁹, which independent of solvent is found in a *syn* configuration.

The spectra of R-stien(fmcH)₂, S-stien(fmcH)₂ and R,S-stien(fmcH)₂ are given in Fig. 1.

The spectra are measured approximately 2 hr after dissolution, at which time *syn/anti* ratio from nmr is estimated to ~10/1. Prolonged dissolution in CHCl₃ seems to accelerate a destruction as the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition intensity falls off markedly after 5 hr. The destruction products have not been investigated.

If one considers absorption and circular dichroism spectra of the two diastereoisomers R- and S-stien(fmcH)₂, it is seen that these fit nicely with expectations based on the order pn < 2,3-bn < stien with respect to increasing barrier towards rotation around the substituted ethylene bridge. This is to say that while R- and S-pn(fmcH)₂, and R- and S-2,3-bn(fmcH)₂ choose the same absolute configuration of the diastereoisomers, this is not the case with R- and S-stien(fmcH)₂ which has a mirror image relationship. A mirror image relation-

ship was also seen with R- and S-chxn(fmcH)₂, and in that case was a consequence of an infinitely great barrier towards rotation around the substituted ethylene bridge. Cooling to -60° does not accentuate the CD-spectra very much and although the absorption spectra do not show a marked exciton splitting there cannot be very much *trans* rotamer present in solution, because of the magnitudes of the Cotton effects.

Turning our attention towards the spectral behaviour of R,S-stien(fmcH)₂, it is seen that the exciton splitting in the absorption band is even less marked than with the active compounds discussed. This means that the distribution between the *gauche* and *trans* rotamers at room temperature is probably placed rather much towards the *trans* form. This conclusion is confirmed by the CD spectrum which is not characteristic of exciton coupling at room temperature, whereas cooling enforces such a behaviour, thereby meaning that this species like the rest of the investigated *meso* and optically inactive diamine condensates with formylcamphor, has the Δ configuration of the chromophores as the low energy one. This set of information supports the conclusion that asymmetric substituents on the ethylene bridge in the condensates of formylcamphor and 1,2-diamines do not directly determine but do influence seriously the way in which minimum potential energy is achieved.

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